

EFFICIENCY OF USE OF HUMAN RESOURCES IN ECONOMIC SECTORS

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Abstract: *The purpose of writing this thesis is to learn the tasks and goals of human resources management and the differences between countries from the experience of developed countries and try it in the practice of Uzbekistan.*

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Human resource management - simply put, it is the internal policy or internal complex function of the organization aimed at recruiting, managing and supporting the people (personnel) who work there and every program and process that affects human performance is part of HR.

Human resource and finance's ability to work together and understand each other's role can be critical to your organization. In many organizations, human resources and finance are two distinct business areas. Finance helps allocate resources to support an organization's goals, maintaining a balance between costs and revenue. HR hires, recruits and motivates people to advance those same goals. This part of HR is often an organization's biggest expense. While they are two different operations, it's important to have collaboration between HR and finance

within an organization. Without that, it will be difficult for those respective entities to fully support organizational objectives.

For an HR and finance collaboration to work, several things need to be considered:

- What is the organization's purpose, and where do these two departments fit into that?
- Does each department understand what the other does?
- What overlap (in duties, personnel, resources) exists between the two, and how can it be best capitalized upon?

The main tasks of HR, i.e. strategic functions, are to ensure that the organization, enterprise and business strategy are in balance, reengineering of the organization's activities, mutual information communication with the employees of the organization, and change management. The HR manager is responsible for monitoring organizational leadership and management culture. Human resource management has 4 tactical functions: staffing, training and development of employees, motivation management, technical services.

In this thesis, we consider how important the efficiency of human resources is in our lives today. The main important motives of HR for companies; risk of losing reputation, improvement of financial indicators. The main tasks of human resource efficiency management are to determine whether the employee is suitable for the job or not, and to ensure that the employees are trained within a certain period of time. Therefore, day by day, organizations and enterprises are focusing their attention first of all on the right selection of HR managers and on bringing the efficiency to a high level during work. David Ulrich, a foreign scholar, has provided some useful structures and ideas about human resources:

David Ulrich Model of HR Roles

Strategic partner - is to influence the development and improvement of the workforce.

Administrative expert - it is the aspect that mainly performs internal work and manages day-to-day expenses

Change agent – based on the activities of internal workers, he performs the role of replacing the agent and providing a good agent to improve the company's activities.

Employee champion - where protecting workers' rights helps ensure their safety and keep them happy and healthy.

The main reasons for the importance of human resources management are:

- Hiring employees based on their talent: that is, HR management department is to attract qualified and responsible persons while assigning positions to employees within the enterprise organization.

- Employee development and professional development: Responsible for training and professional development of employees. Improving the skills of employees according to the needs of the times plays an important role in improving the performance of employees.

- Attracting and retaining employees: creating a positive work environment for employees in this department. Incentives for good performance and awareness of well-being go a long way in employee retention and loyalty.

- Personnel policy and compliance: HR ensures that the company's employees work according to the rules of the law and the organization's standards. And it is to provide employees with monthly salaries and workplace security. And it provides justice to disputes and disagreements in the relationship between the employee and the employer during the work.

Every operating company has HR management, and in every country, organizations operate according to their standard laws. Therefore, each country has its own characteristics of HR. Therefore, if we look outside of Uzbekistan, European countries, Asian countries, all of them have their own special tasks and goals of HR. It does not necessarily mean that HR does not perform the same task, the goal is the same, but there will be changes based on the country's law and people's skills.

HR management in foreign countries involves managing human resources in a global context, where organizations operate across international borders and deal with diverse cultural, legal, and economic environments. It requires a deep understanding of local laws, customs, and practices, as well as the ability to navigate cross-cultural differences and adapt HR strategies and practices accordingly.

Every country has its own characteristics in terms of practical and scientific management of human resources. The goal of HR management in European and Asian countries is the same, but the tasks and operations performed are fundamentally different. For example, in terms of legal and employment practices in Europe, employees are legally provided with vacation, working time and severance pay. For workers in Asia, labor rights provide flexibility rights depending on the situation. In terms of performance management, individuality is emphasized in Europe, while in Asian countries, team work is highly valued.

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